
WHITE PAPER

Employing National Guard Cyber Forces in Title 32 Status for National Cyber Missions

Operational Support to DoD and Active Component Customers

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A summary of findings in a full Title 32 Cyber Study

NIPR: <https://go.intelink.gov/t32study>

JWICS: <https://go.ic.gov/t32study>

Interactive public web site: <https://t32cyber.org>

Executive Summary

The National Guard possesses significant cyber talent that remains underutilized for national defense. This white paper summarizes research findings demonstrating that National Guard cyber forces can support certain national defensive cyber missions while in Title 32 status, under existing law and policy, when a training requirement is met. The core barrier is not an absence of legal authority but a governance and execution gap — ambiguous implementing guidance, institutional risk aversion, and fragmented coordination mechanisms that prevent systematic utilization.

These findings are drawn from doctoral research at Dakota State University (DSU), in partnership with the University of Wisconsin–Madison and Wisconsin National Guard (WING), incorporating documentary analysis of statutes, DoD and National Guard Bureau (NGB) policy, and joint doctrine; an expert survey of practitioners; and an operational case study of the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP), a Title 32 cyber mission-support pilot. The research examined feasible mission types for Title 32 support to DoD customers, with particular focus on Defensive Cyberspace Operations–Internal Defensive Measures (DCO-IDM) (cyberspace defense), Department of Defense Information Network (DoDIN) Operations (cyberspace security), cybersecurity situational awareness, cyber support to intelligence, and DCO–Response Actions (DCO-RA) (cyberspace exploitation).

Bottom line: Documentary evidence, expert consensus, and the operational case study strongly support defensive, advisory, support, and research missions as feasible under Title 32 under existing law and policy. The primary barriers identified are fear of misinterpretation, lack of implementing guidance, and active component bias — not legal or policy prohibitions.

The Problem

The Department of Defense faces a persistent shortfall in cyber capacity. Demand for Cyber Mission Force (CMF) capabilities continues to grow, yet recruiting and retaining qualified cyber operators remains a department-wide challenge. Meanwhile, approximately 3,900 National Guard Soldiers and Airmen serve in dedicated cyber units across 54 states and territories. Many hold civilian-acquired skills in cybersecurity, network defense, intelligence analysis, and information technology that directly map to DoD cyber mission requirements.

Despite this capacity, National Guard cyber forces are rarely employed in support of national cyber missions while in their primary duty status: Title 32. Instead, Guard cyber personnel are typically utilized only through Title 10 mobilizations, which remove service members from civilian employment, disrupt unit readiness cycles, and treat the Guard as a surge or plug-in force rather than a routinely integrated component of national cyber defense. When not mobilized, many Guard cyber operators train on simulated scenarios with limited connection to real-world mission requirements, contributing to skill atrophy and retention challenges.

Congress has repeatedly signaled concern about this underutilization. Section 1651 of the FY2017 NDAA directed the Army to develop a strategy to incorporate Reserve Component Cyber Protection Teams (CPTs) into the CMF. Subsequent NDAA provisions have continued to call for better leveraging of Guard cyber expertise. Most recently, Section 1544 of the [FY2026 NDAA](#) directs a study on Reserve Component integration into the CMF — the latest in a decade-long pattern of congressional studies without mandated implementation.

Legal and Policy Framework

The research finds that existing statutory authorities, DoD policy, and joint doctrine already provide a legal pathway for Title 32 cyber support to national missions when properly structured around training requirements.

Core Authorities

[32 USC §502\(a\)](#) governs regular drills and annual training. [32 USC §502\(f\)](#) authorizes additional full-time National Guard duty for training and “other duty” (and under 502(f)(2) as prescribed by the President or Secretary of Defense). Together, these provisions form the statutory foundation for Title 32 mission-aligned training — “operations incident to training.”

[DoDI 1215.06](#) explicitly encourages the use of Reserve Component training duty to support operational requirements while maintaining readiness. The 2024 [Domestic Operational Law Handbook](#) further clarifies that National Guard personnel in Title 32 status may conduct cyberspace operations when the primary purpose is training and mission support is incidental.

The Training-Mission Construct

The critical legal principle is straightforward: the primary purpose of the activity must be military training; mission support may occur as an incidental consequence of performing that training. This construct is not novel — it is the same principle that underlies the Federated Intelligence Program (FIP), codified in [NGR 350-1](#), under which Title 32 intelligence personnel perform real-world analysis in support of national requirements while satisfying training objectives.

The research proposes extending this established model to cyberspace operations through a Federated Cyber Program (FCP) mission support model, in which Title 32 cyber personnel perform real-world cybersecurity and defensive cyber activities aligned with their unit Mission Essential Task Lists (METLs) while simultaneously providing operationally relevant support to DoD mission partners. Of note, a successful pilot of this model — known as the [Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program \(WIFCP\)](#) — has been operational in Wisconsin since 2021.

Innovative Readiness Training

Innovative Readiness Training (IRT) does not apply. The IRT statute ([10 USC §2012](#)) and policy ([DoDI 1100.24](#)) cover use of National Guard cyber forces to support *non-DoD* customers *outside* DoD, and thus does not apply to DoD operational support (OS) and AC mission support.

Feasible Mission Types for Title 32 Support

The research identifies a spectrum of cyberspace operations ranging from those with strong consensus for Title 32 feasibility to those requiring additional authorization.

Mission Type	Expert Consensus	Assessment
DCO-IDM (Cyberspace Defense)	86.2%	Strongest consensus. Actions conducted within the defended environment to protect, monitor, detect, analyze, and mitigate threats. Well-aligned with CPT training tasks and METL requirements.
DoDIN Operations (Cyberspace Security)	86.2%	Equally strong consensus. Threat-informed security actions within protected cyberspace, conducted in advance of specific compromise. Directly supports network defense posture.
DoDIN Operations (System Operation)	85.0%	Near-equivalent support. Routine system operations and maintenance within the DoDIN.
Cybersecurity Situational Awareness	N/A (Case Study)	Demonstrated by WIFCP. Open-source and commercial cyber threat monitoring, research, and reporting for DoD partners. Not an intelligence activity when properly scoped.
Cyber Support to Intel or Intel Support to Cyber	N/A (Operational Precedent)	Established under the Federated Intelligence Program (FIP) in NGR 350-1. Intelligence personnel operate under existing IO compliance frameworks. FCP concept extends analogous model to cyber.
DCO-RA (Cyberspace Exploitation)	57.0%	Mixed support due to lack of survey granularity on Cyberspace Exploitation vs. Cyberspace Attack; however, the 2024 DOPLAW Handbook notes that Cyberspace Exploitation activities under DCO-RA may be conducted as OS incident to training when the supported federal mission is consistent with the NG unit's training requirements.

Key distinction: DCO-IDM, DoDIN Operations, and cybersecurity situational awareness involve actions *within* the defended network environment (internal cyberspace operations). DCO-RA involves response actions that may extend *beyond* the defended environment, raising additional authorization considerations. The legal boundary that separates clearly permissible Title 32 training activities from those requiring federal orders is often described as the “kill chain boundary.” In the context of DCO-RA or OCO, this would be the Cyberspace Attack function.

What the Experts Say

A survey of 151 respondents across military, civilian, academic, and industry sectors provided empirical insight into practitioner perspectives on Title 32 cyber employment. Respondents included National Guard and active component personnel, DoD civilians, defense contractors, and academic researchers with deep expertise in cyber operations and military law.

Key Quantitative Findings

- **79.7%** agree or strongly agree that current federal law and policy allow National Guard cyber personnel to support AC cyber missions or operational support of national cyber missions while in Title 32 status.
- **84.7%** agree or strongly agree that Title 32 activities can be structured to meet training requirements and contribute to national mission objectives simultaneously.
- **86.2%** identify DCO-IDM and DoDIN Operations as feasible mission types under Title 32 with a training requirement.
- **66.7%** believe federated support from multiple states can be scaled effectively to support national cyber objectives while in Title 32 status.
- **70.0%** support explicit NDAA language codifying Title 32 national cyber missions; only 3.3% oppose.
- **Mean confidence score of 5.67/10** that Title 32 authorities can operationally support national cyber missions without new legislation — indicating the barrier is implementation clarity, not statutory absence.
- **Mean benefit score of 7.90/10** for creating a structured national program to align National Guard cyber personnel with national mission needs.

Five Major Themes from Qualitative Analysis

Reflexive thematic analysis of open-ended expert responses produced five major themes that collectively describe the landscape of constraints, enablers, and operational realities:

#	Theme	Frequency	Top Finding
1	Legal and Policy Ambiguity	35.2%	Lack of implementing guidance is the single most cited barrier (31.4% of coded responses)
2	Precedent Exists but Poorly Recognized	31.0%	Precedent and training-task alignment already demonstrated informally in multiple states
3	Operational Feasibility and High Training Value	11.0%	Real-world mission alignment improves readiness; remote operations expand access
4	Cultural and Institutional Resistance	24.8%	Active component bias (18.1%) and service parochialism are significant but not insurmountable barriers
5	Demand for a Federated Cyber Program	35.2%	Strong demand for formal mission manager constructs, national-state linkages, and recurring structured tasking

Dominant practitioner view: The barriers are procedural and knowledge-based, not legal. Many leaders and planners do not fully understand how to properly employ National Guard cyber assets under existing authorities. The landscape is confusing, and organizational barriers and risk aversion substitute for clear prohibition. Additionally, some approval authorities provide incomplete or incorrect information about the ability to conduct allowed activities under Title 32.

Proof of Concept: The Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program

The [Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program \(WIFCP\)](#) provides applied evidence that Title 32 cyber mission support works in practice. Established in 2021 under a Memorandum of Agreement between the Wisconsin National Guard and a DoD mission partner, WIFCP utilizes the 176th Cyber Protection Team to provide cybersecurity research and situational awareness.

Program Design

- **Mission:** Open-source and commercial cyber threat monitoring, research, and reporting for a DoD partner's area of responsibility. Activities were explicitly scoped as cybersecurity, not intelligence or intelligence-related activity.
- **Authority:** Title 32 duty statuses under 32 USC §502, including drill-for-points (unpaid), regular drill, and annual training. No new statutory language, policy waivers, or experimental authorities were required.
- **Training alignment:** All program activities were linked to unit METL requirements and USCYBERCOM-specified Mission Essential Tasks for Cyber Protection Teams.
- **Oversight:** Program was briefed to the DoD partner organization Director, Senior Military Official, Army G2, ARNG G2, NGB J2 IO, NGB IG, and State JAG.

Documented Outcomes

- 17 weekly Cyber News Summaries produced during the study period (January–April 2025)
- Over 1,600 open-source articles reviewed and synthesized
- Products distributed to more than 300 recipients within the partner organization
- Repeated partner feedback that reporting was valuable and used for briefing and analysis
- Two enlisted cyber Soldiers attributed reenlistment decisions directly to meaningful mission work in drilling status
- **Estimated \$800,000 retention impact** based on stated replacement training costs (~\$400,000 per fully-qualified 17C Soldier)

WIFCP demonstrates the “art of the possible” — proving that Title 32 cyber personnel can deliver operationally relevant support to national mission partners while meeting training requirements under existing authority. The pilot also highlights the force management value of meaningful engagement: retaining trained cyber operators who might otherwise separate from military service.

Mission-Specific Application to DoD Customers

The following describes how each mission type can be structured for Title 32 support to DoD customers, with the training requirement as the primary purpose and mission support as an incidental benefit.

DCO-IDM (Cyberspace Defense)

Cyber Protection Teams conduct threat hunting, malware analysis, vulnerability assessment, and incident response within the defended environment of a supported DoD command. These activities directly map to CPT METL requirements and represent the highest-consensus mission type for Title 32 employment. Guard CPTs that have previously deployed on Title 10 mobilizations (such as Task Force Echo) can maintain proficiency by continuing similar defensive work during Title 32 drill and training periods.

DoDIN Operations (Cyberspace Security)

National Guard cyber personnel conduct threat-informed security assessments, compliance monitoring, security architecture review, and defensive configuration within protected DoDIN segments. These proactive, threat-agnostic security actions align with both the Protect and Identify functions of the NIST Cybersecurity Framework and are well within the scope of routine Title 32 training activities.

Cybersecurity Situational Awareness

As demonstrated by WIFCP, Guard cyber personnel can monitor open-source and commercial threat reporting, produce cyber news summaries, and deliver situational awareness products to supported commands. This mission type is low-risk from an authorities perspective (it does not require DoDIN access or intelligence authorities), yet delivers high value to mission partners who lack the capacity for continuous threat environment monitoring.

Intelligence Support to Cyber

The Federated Intelligence Program (FIP) already establishes the precedent and policy framework for Title 32 intelligence personnel supporting national requirements. Under FIP, ARNG military intelligence Soldiers perform real-world analysis using Intelligence Readiness and Operations Capability (IROC), ensuring continuous preparation for validated missions. The FCP concept extends this model to cyber personnel, with appropriate coordination with intelligence oversight to ensure activities are properly scoped.

DCO-RA (Cyberspace Exploitation)

Response actions that extend beyond the defended environment involve additional authorization considerations. However, the 2024 Domestic Operational Law Handbook notes that Cyberspace Exploitation activities under DCO-RA may be conducted as operational support when the supported federal mission is consistent with the Guard unit's training requirements, the federal component can perform its mission without Guard support, and Guard personnel are not

employed full-time under Title 32 for the federal mission. DCO-RA activities should be approached with greater caution and more rigorous legal review than DCO-IDM or DoDIN Operations, but are not categorically excluded.

Funding and Governance

Survey respondents emphasized the importance of sustained resourcing for Title 32 cyber mission support. On a 0–10 scale, respondents rated the importance of customer-provided funding as follows:

- **Full-time orders: 7.69** (e.g., Tour of Duty, ADOS)
- **Ad hoc orders: 7.64** (e.g., additional training periods)
- **Specialized training: 7.73**

Respondents indicated that funding management should involve the supported customer (Combatant Command or Combat Support Agency) at 74.1%, the National Guard Bureau at 56.9%, and the Service Cyber Component at 51.7%. The preferred funding mechanism is a Military Interdepartmental Purchase Request (MIPR) from the supported agency to NGB, then to the State and unit — enabling reimbursable support without requiring Title 10 mobilization.

A critical finding: respondents rated the importance of a mission manager being on full-time orders at 7.12/10, but rated the importance of the manager being in Title 10 status at only 5.30/10. This indicates the need for *continuity and availability* — not necessarily Title 10 status — for effective program management.

Legislative Context: FY2026 NDAA

Section 1544 of the FY2026 NDAA directs the Secretary of Defense to study integration of Reserve Component personnel into the CMF and cyberspace operations. However, compared to the stronger Senate Armed Services Committee language in Section 1605, the final enacted version removed the implementation plan mandate, force-structure optimization requirements, funding assessments, interim congressional briefings, and requirement for legislative recommendations.

This legislative narrowing is consistent with a decade-long pattern in which Congress acknowledges the value of Guard cyber expertise but defers resolution to the Department of Defense. The pattern reinforces the study's central finding: the primary barrier is not statutory absence but institutional willingness to implement existing authorities.

Implication for senior leaders

Waiting for new legislation is unlikely to resolve Title 32 cyber employment challenges. The Department already possesses sufficient authority to act. What is needed is implementing guidance, governance structures, and institutional commitment to execution.

Recommendations

A. Organizational and Structural

- Designate clear points of responsibility within U.S. Cyber Command and the National Guard Bureau for developing and overseeing Title 32 cyber integration.
- Formalize mission manager roles for federated cyber programs, analogous to the Federated Intelligence Program, to coordinate requirements, tasking, and feedback between national mission partners and Guard units.
- Encourage states to establish cyber integration working groups (TAG, state J-staff, key unit leaders) to oversee Title 32 cyber initiatives and align state and federal priorities.

B. Governance and Implementation

- Develop a formal **Title 32 Cyber Integration Profile** specifying mission categories appropriate for Title 32 support (DCO-IDM, DoDIN Ops, cybersecurity situational awareness) and the conditions, oversight, and expected outcomes for each.
- Establish standardized request and approval artifacts — templates for training alignment documentation, legal review, and oversight — to reduce the case-by-case negotiation burden currently borne by individual units and states.
- Create standardized metrics and reporting (number of federated programs, training hours logged on mission, mission impact assessments) to enable oversight and congressional visibility.

C. Strategic Alignment and Policy Development

- Develop a **National Guard Cyber Integration Strategy** describing how Title 32 supports national objectives, how it relates to the Cyber Mission Force, and how it contributes to broader multi-domain operations posture.
- Use the FY2026 NDAA Section 1544 study as a roadmap for assessing authorities, leveraging civilian-acquired skills, and identifying billets, infrastructure, and barriers — consistent with the findings in this research.
- Incorporate lessons from pilots like WIFCP into joint and service doctrine and policy so federated Title 32 models become recognized options — like FIP — rather than one-off experiments.

Conclusion

The United States does not primarily face an authorities gap for employing National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for certain defensive national cyber missions. It faces a governance and execution gap.

Existing statutes, DoD policy, joint doctrine, and established precedent collectively provide sufficient authority to integrate Guard cyber forces into national missions when structured around training requirements. The barriers — ambiguous implementing guidance, institutional risk aversion, active component bias, and the absence of standardized governance mechanisms — are real, but they are addressable through policy clarification and institutional commitment rather than new legislation.

The National Guard offers the Department of Defense a geographically distributed, civilian-skilled, dual-status cyber force that can be routinely engaged in meaningful defensive cyber work without the disruption and cost of Title 10 mobilization. Realizing this potential requires treating Title 32 cyber integration not as a peripheral force management question, but as a core element of national cybersecurity governance.

Full Research Report

NIPR: <https://go.intelink.gov/t32study>

JWICS: <https://go.ic.gov/t32study>

Interactive public web site: <https://t32cyber.org>

Full Research Report: <https://t32cyber.org/report>

Survey Data Explorer: <https://t32cyber.org/results>

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